

Additional File 2. Dosages of immunosuppressive drugs per patient enrolled in The ONE Study reference group at each time point

	- 4 weeks PRE transplant		+ 8 weeks POST transplant		+ 36 weeks POST transplant		+ 60 weeks POST transplant	
	#003	#004	#003	#004	#003	#004	#003	#004
Tacrolimus trough levels (ng/ml)	-	-	10.6	10.6	9.9	5.8	9.1	4.3
target levels (ng/ml)	-	-	3-10		3-8		3-6	
Prednisolone (mg/day)	-	-	10		0		0	
MMF (g/day)	-	-	1.5		1.5		1.5	
Basiliximab (mg)	-	-	0		0		0	